

SHORT COMMUNICATION

RNA isolation from paraffinated material of histological's prepared slides

Matheus Moreira Perez¹, Alexandre Luiz Affonso Fonseca¹, Fábio Prosdocimi², Bianca Bianco¹, Fernando Luiz Affonso Fonseca^{1,3}, Beatriz da Costa Aguiar Alves¹

 OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Perez MM, Fonseca ALA, Prosdocimi F, Bianco B, Fonseca FLA, Alves BCA. RNA isolation from paraffinated material of histological's prepared slides. *MicroMed*. 2017; 5(2): 60-62.

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.942443>

Received: June 13, 2017

Revised: September 12, 2017

Accepted: September 18, 2017

Copyright: © 2017 Perez MM, et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.
www.journals.tmkarpinski.com/index.php/mmed

Transparency declaration: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical considerations: FMABC Ethics Committee (protocol number 384/2007).

¹ Faculdade de Medicina do ABC, Av. Príncipe de Gales, 821, 09060-650, Santo André, SP, Brazil

² Universidade Paulista, São Paulo, SP, Brazil

³ Instituto de Ciências Farmacêuticas da Universidade Federal de São Paulo, R. Prof. Artur Riedel, 275, 09972-270 Diadema, SP, Brazil

*Corresponding Author: Fernando Luiz Affonso Fonseca; Laboratório de Análises Clínicas, Faculdade de Medicina do ABC, Av. Príncipe de Gales, 821, Santo André, SP, Brasil, CEP: 9060-650; E-mail: profferfonseca@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The paraffinization of solid biopsies allows a better preservation and preparation of microscopy slides used for histological evaluations. Techniques of RNA extraction are suitable to be applied in microtomed paraffinated material, but the extraction of paraffinic material already disposed in a slide has not yet been described and can be useful for gene expression studies. We adapted the RNA isolation technique of paraffinated material for slide-laid paraffinated material, using the Rneasy® FFPE Kit. Total RNA so isolated is suitable to gene expression analysis by RT-qPCR.

Keywords: Paraffinated material; Slides; RNA isolation.

Advances in molecular biology and its techniques, such as RT-qPCR and genomic and proteomic sequencing, provide the elucidation of the functioning of our genetic material, its molecular mechanisms and its relation to the phenotypic characteristics of each individual of the most varied species, both from the physiological as well as pathological point of view.

Recently, gene expression studies have generated a lot of fundamental information for a better understanding of the adaptive and pathological changes related to diseases such as cancer, besides characterizing biological markers that facilitate the diagnosis and the prognostic monitoring of several disorders. Among the techniques most used in this type of study, RT-qPCR - which consists of quantifying the expression of genes of interest by means of the amplification of cDNA fragments in real time, synthesized from the RNA isolated from several types of biological material - stands out. One of the major limiting factors for adequate reaction efficiency is the quality of the biological material. It is known that RNA is a very instable molecule and the sample condition, such as the RNA extraction technique, may partially damage or completely degrade the molecule, if certain concerns are overlooked [1].

Often, solid biopsy may be fixed in formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) and blocked for performing arrangements in slides, consisting on the most adequate way for retrospective histological studies, in addition to allowing the storage and preservation of genetic material for a long time. Despite RNA isolation

from FFPE tissues leads to a highly degraded total RNA [1], these FFPE block samples may be used for nucleic acids extraction aiming to perform genome and gene expression studies [2, 3]. RNA extraction techniques for gene expression studies from FFPE tissue after microtomy are already well described and kits with this purpose are commercialized [4, 5]; however, this procedure in paraffin-embedded material fixed in a slide has not yet been described and there are no protocols and kits for this purpose.

This study aims to describe an adaptation in the technique of RNA isolation from slide-laid FFPE tissues, allowing these samples to provide the quality and concentration suitable for the realization of RT-qPCR using a known commercial kit.

Total RNA isolation were performed in 30 formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded biopsies of oral squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) that were microtomed and disposed in slides for histological studies. Before biopsies, all patients have signed an Informed Consent Term in compliance with the Helsinki Convention and approved by FMABC Ethics Committee (protocol number 384/2007). The material of the slides was scraped off completely and transferred to a 2 ml microtube with the aid of a scalpel slide, requiring at least three slides for each sample to obtain an adequate amount of material to perform the extraction. After scraping of slides, the isolation of total RNA was performed with the RNeasy® FFPE Kit (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA) and xylene was used as deparaffinization agent. The steps outlined in the kit protocol were followed closely.

The cDNA of the samples was synthesized using the SuperScript® III Reverse Transcriptase kit (Invitrogen, cat no 11752050, following the manufacturer's protocol), using random primers, and subjected to RT-qPCR in the Applied Biosystems® 7500 Real-Time PCR Systems (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) for the amplification of a 148 bp fragment of the endogenous gene GAPDH. The RT-qPCR was prepared to a final volume of 15 µl containing: 1X SYBR Green mix (Quantitec SYBR Green PCR kit, QIAGEN cat. no. 204054), 10 pmol of each specific primer (F-GACCACAGTCCATGCCAT and R-CAGCTCAGGGATGACCTT) and 2 µl cDNA. The primer was designed with the help of the software Primer3 Input 0.4.0 software, available at <http://frodo.wi.mit.edu/primer3>. The sequence was checked for specificity by the Primer-BLAST program, available at <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/tools/primer-blast>. The MCF7 cells cDNA amplification was used as reaction standard for comparison of amplification pattern and melt curve. The cyclic parameters were an initial hot start step at 95°C for 10 min, followed by 40 repetitions of 95°C for 15 sec and 60°C for 25 sec.

The concentration and quality of RNA obtained were measured in NanoVue®. The mean concentration of RNA extracted was 0.95 µg/µl, ranging from 0.025 µg/µl to 4.9 µg/µl, depending on the amount of biological material available. A260/A280 absorbance ratio obtained with these samples averaged 1.46, ranging from 0.98 to 1.84. The average A260/A280 ratio for FFPE tissue is 1.47, close to the average value obtained in this study [6].

Figure 1. a) Melting curve of GAPDH amplification in all CEC samples. b) Amplification Plot of GAPDH gene. Curve of expression in blue belongs to standard curve (MCF7). All of the others belong to CEC samples.

Because RNA from FFPE samples does not have the same quality as RNA from fresh samples, it is possible that the poly-A tail of the transcript is not intact [7]. For this reason, reverse transcription was performed with random primers as an alternative to oligo-dT. The melt amplification and curve graphs of the samples and the MCF7 (in blue) are shown in Figure 1. The melt temperatures (around 87°C) are similar between all samples and standard (MCF7 cells), showing that the amplified product is the same.

Although RNA extracted from both paraffin embedded and slide-laid material does not have the same A260/A230 absorbance ratio of fresh samples, amplification of the endogenous GAPDH gene was satisfactory for all samples. For this reason, the adaptation of the protocol of RNA extraction from FFPE tissues laid on histological slides proved to be efficient to obtain adequate material for gene expression studies.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

MMP: designed the study and performed all experiments; ALAF and FP: provided all CEC biological samples and designed the study; BB, FLAF and BCAA: analyzed the results and prepared the manuscript. The final manuscript was read and approved by all authors.

REFERENCES

1. Wang Z, Lebron JA, Wolf JJ. Reliable quantification of mRNA in archived formalin-fixed tissue with or without paraffin embedding. *J Pharmacol Toxicol Methods*. 2015; 71: 103-109.
2. Ribeiro-Silva A, Garcia SB. Estudo comparativo de três diferentes procedimentos para extração de RNA a partir de amostras fixadas em formalina e embebidas em parafina. *J Brasil Patol Med Labor*. 2008; 44: 123-130.
3. Klopffleisch R, Weiss AT, Gruber AD. Excavation of a buried treasure - DNA, mRNA, miRNA and protein analysis in formalin fixed, paraffin embedded tissues. *Histol Histopathol*. 2011; 26(6): 797-810.
4. Kuniyoshi RK, Gehrke FS, Alves BCA, Vilas-Bôas V, Coló AE, Sousa N, et al. Gene profiling and circulating tumor cells as biomarker to prognostic of patients with locoregional breast cancer. *Tumor Biol*. 2015; 36(10): 8075-8083.
5. Germini D, Gehrke FS, Lira D, Alves BCA, Azzalis L, Perez MM, et al. hMSH2 and hMSH6 gene expression profiles in colorectal adenocarcinoma in patients up to 50 years of age. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2016; 83: 602-606.
6. Lam B, Simkin M, Rghei N, Haj-Ahmad Y. Revised guidelines for RNA quality assessment for diverse biological sample input. Norhen Biotek Corporation 2012; APP47-v1. Available from: https://norgenbiotek.com/sites/default/files/resources/urine_total_rna_purification_maxi_kit_slurry_format_revised_guidelines_for_rna_quality_assessment_for_diverse_biological_sample_input_application_notes_238.pdf
7. Penland SK, Keku TO, Torrice C, He X, Krishnamurthy J, Hoadley KA, et al. RNA expression analysis of formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tumors. *Lab Invest*. 2007; 87(4): 383-391.